

LEVERAGING VALUE STREAM DIAGRAMS TO ILLUSTRATE DIGITAL PRESERVATION'S PLACE WITHIN AN INFORMATION-DRIVEN ORGANIZATION

Jeanne Kramer-Smyth - World Bank Group Archives

Context: As part of an Agile Transformation taking place across the World Bank's Information and Technology Solutions' Vice Presidency, our Information Governance & Archives (ITSAR) team re-envisioned our work program using a value stream diagram to clarify how the duties of our work program exist both in service to the information and the community that creates and uses it.

- Lessons Learned:**
- The value stream diagram made clear that our digital preservation program's success relies on the solid foundation created by information governance and in-place records management.
 - These insights support strategic planning and provide management with new ways to advocate for digital preservation resources.

ITSAR STAFF ensure all the above by creating policy, applying governance, delivering training, providing services, implementing and integrating systems, and coordinating with application teams across the Bank . We arrange, describe, disclose, digitize, make discoverable, and respond to requests for the information in custody.